

Semi-solid-state Li-ion batteries functionally integrated in composite structures for next generation hybrid electric airliner

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Reviewer	Alexander Beutl (AIT)	2024-03-15
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Nomenclature

Acronym / Short Name	
C	Graphite
CCF	Coated Carbon Fibres
CF	Carbon Fibre
EOL	End of Life
KPI	Key-Performance-Indicator
LIB	Lithium-ion battery
NMCxyz	$\text{LiNi}_{0.x}\text{Mn}_{0.y}\text{Co}_{0.z}\text{O}_2$
NMP	<i>N</i> -Methyl-2-pyrrolidone
RMS	Reinforced Multilayer Stack
Si/C	Silicon nanoparticles/graphite composite
SoH	State of Health
SotA	State-of-the-art
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
WIP	Warm isostatic pressing

1. Introduction

The SOLIFLY project is developing two concepts for structural batteries and its integration in composite materials resulting in an innovative hybrid material, which can be employed as energy storage as well as load-bearing structural part of future aircraft. While a TRL 4 is targeted in the SOLIFLY project and development activities are carried out at lab scale, the project was designed to also address potentially upcoming challenges in the technology development after the end of the project. One aspect of this upcoming challenges is the manufacturability of the battery cell concepts at a larger scale, which is crucial to making the technology widely available for industry. This deliverable contains the results of the manufacturability assessment as part of WP4.1 (Airworthiness and manufacturability assessment), which analyses the applicability of state-of-the-art battery cell production to the proposed battery cell concepts. For this, potential production processes for both battery cell concepts (coated carbon fibres (CCF) and reinforced multilayered stack (RMS)) were identified as close as possible related to existing techniques in the SotA battery cell manufacturing followed by an assessment of the transferability of the existing processes. The proposed process steps are visualized as flow diagrams following the colour code: green = process available in battery cell production and high transferability; yellow = process available in battery cell production and low-mid transferability; red = process not available in battery cell production.

The manufacturability assessment is complemented by the TRL assessment of the current state of the technologies, a proposed TRL step-up, and an exploitation plan as part of WP4.2 (Ex-post TRL assessment and step-up plan, exploitation plan, and WP4 final workshop).

The outcome of the manufacturability assessment was presented at the WP4 workshop and public event on November 20-21, 2023 in Naples, enabling fast transfer of the SOLIFLY results to the public, research, and industry.

2. Manufacturability

For the assessment of the manufacturability, a defined process chain is needed. Therefore, a potential battery manufacturing process is briefly described in section 2.1 (Process). A more detailed description of the steps is given in the sections 2.2-2.5 and a conclusion of the manufacturability is provided in section 2.6 (Conclusion of the manufacturability assessment). For the assessment of this potential production process, preceding activities such as supply-chain and quality assessment of the used materials is obligated. Therefore, only requirements for the production will be discussed here.

2.1 Process

A potential industrial-scale process should be as close as possible to already established production processes from the battery production industry. Therefore, a manufacturing process should be targeted which leverages a high TRL of known processes from already established conventional pouch cell production (Figure 1). The conventional approach to produce a pouch battery cell can be divided into the manufacturing of the electrode, the cell assembly, and the cell finishing [1].

1. Electrode manufacturing

2. Cell assembly

3. Cell finishing

Figure 1: Industrially established pouch-cell production process chain.

However, the use of the non-conventional components such as CCF based electrodes and a structural electrolyte necessitates tweaking of these procedures and the introduction of additional steps. One of these additional steps is the production of the semi-solid electrolyte, while the handling of this type of electrolyte also impacts the cell assembly. Additionally, the structural integration of the electrochemical active components into the composite material requires an extra step, which needs to be scaled-up for industrial manufacturing. To better assess the manufacturability of the structural battery, the processing steps are discussed in the following subsections 2.2 – 2.5. Although it was shown that the exposure of the electrolyte formulations to moist air does not lead to the evolution of highly toxic hydrofluoric acid, the production of the battery cells should be employing dry-room-conditions for all steps, which involves the electrolyte without sealing of the battery cell under dry atmosphere. Dry-rooms are already established in the LIB-production process and ensure the safe handling of the water sensitive materials as well as ensure the electrochemical performance [2].

2.2 Electrode Manufacturing

Two electrode concepts were employed in this project, which differ in their transferability to the state-of-the-art battery cell production process. The potential electrode manufacturing process for an RMS-type (concept #2) battery cell resembles the conventional process: The active materials needed are dry mixed with the needed additives and dispersed in an organic solvent. This process can be designed as batch-process, or an extruder can be used for continuous mixing. Since the electrodes used for the RMS approach are using well established active materials, existing know-how can be leveraged and only minor changes to recipes need to be made to optimize their use in the RMS-type cell mainly driven by the addition of the electrolyte formulation into the slurry. This adjustment is needed to ensure the ionic conductivity from the active materials to the gel electrolyte (more details in confidential deliverable D2.1 [3]) but impacts the rheological properties of the slurry which needs to be optimized for the coating process [4].

Figure 2: Schematic illustration of cell concept cross-sections: a) conventional pouch cell, b) RMS cell concept, c) CCF cell concept.

The resulting slurry can then be processed on established production lines: The active slurries are coated on current collector foils using applications systems such as slot dies, comma bars or anilox roller. Solvent-removal can be achieved by wide-spread convection dryers or similar technologies like infra-red drying and finally the coated foils are compacted by hot-calendering. Compared to SotA conventional electrodes, the active material needs to be as compacted as possible (e.g. porosity needs to be as low as possible), if the electrolyte is part of the active material composition. If needed, the rolled-up electrode foils can be subdued to vacuum drying to eliminate residual moisture, sealed, and stored before further processing [1].

Figure 3: Potential process chain for the electrode manufacturing for concept #2 resembling a conventional approach with low degree adjustments.

Manufacturing of electrodes for the CCF-type battery cell on the other hand necessitates the introduction of new steps and has a significant lower degree of transferability to established electrode production processes.

In a first step, the exchange of the conventional current collectors for carbon fibers urges a high degree of knowledge and technology transfer from carbon-fiber processing industries. This includes the parallel,

dense alignment of the carbon fibers without damaging the fibers to minimize the probability of short circuits in the final battery cell, a uniform coating of the carbon fibers with the modified conventional active material slurries and the handling of the coated carbon fibers for drying, calendaring and vacuum drying. A potential

roll-to-roll process might be possible starting with commercially available unidirectional carbon fiber tapes, which necessitates the introduction of a fiber-spreading assembly unit. Alternatively, spread carbon fiber tapes fixed on adhesive grids might be used as starting material if their use does not lower the electrical or mechanical performance of the battery cell. As this investigation was not in the scope of the SOLIFLY project, further development is needed to identify the best possible carbon fiber raw material for industrial procession in electrode manufacturing while being compatible with structural requirements. Additionally, the application of a tab (Cu, or metal coated foil) in defined intervals is needed [5]. The connection from the CCFs to the current collector (e.g. by gluing) is not a defined process in the current battery production, therefore this step needs to be established.

The spread carbon fiber can then be coated with the active material slurry already described for the manufacturing of the RMS-concept electrodes. Other coating techniques can be adapted from carbon-fiber handling industries to improve the coating results but at the costs of the transferability.

In all cases, changes to the recipes might be necessary to adapt this process step to the spread carbon fibers. The coating of the spread carbon fibers by conventional coating processes established in the pouch cell production process, necessitates further optimization in order to get a homogenous coating of the carbon fibers. Better coating results and therefore eventually better performance of the structural battery might be achievable by dipping the carbon fibers into a bath of active materials slurry without any substrate to ensure coating of the CFs from all directions. This step however is not established in the electrode manufacturing industry, so additional investments and development is needed.

Drying, calendaring and vacuum drying of the coated fibers can be realized by employing established processes and no or only minor adjustments (e.g., longer drying times) are needed.

Figure 4: Potential process chain for the electrode manufacturing for concept #1 as close as possible to a conventional approach with major adjustments for the carbon fiber preparation and mid-low degree adjustments for the further process steps.

2.3 Electrolyte Manufacturing

In SotA conventional pouch cell production, the electrolyte needs to be handled in a dry room due to the sensitivity towards humidity. If the proposed electrolyte formulation does not react in a humid atmosphere, this requirement could be eliminated. However, the use of a semi-solid electrolyte is not industrially established and therefore development of adapted processes is needed.

The electrolyte is produced by combining a solution of the lithium salt in an ionic liquid with a gelling agent in NMP. Nanoparticles are introduced as additive to improve the mechanical stability of the electrolyte. The viscosity of the slurry is a key factor for the processing on existing production technology limiting the solids content in the slurry mixture.

With this condition, the slurry preparation can be adapted from the processing of the active materials described in the electrode manufacturing process. Dry mixing of the solid components and dispersion in the ionic liquid solution of the lithium salt can both employ existing technology and knowledge from the SotA battery cell production facilities. However, the current recipe might need adjustments for the industrial scale process. New production lines need to be installed to ensure there is no contamination of the active material lines with the electrolyte. To avoid additional substrate for the electrolyte manufacturing and

simplification of the cell assembly, the casting of the electrolyte dispersion directly onto the electrodes (concepts #1 and #2) should be implemented. Additionally, the contact of the electrolyte with the active material and therefore a good ionic conductivity is ensured, employing this approach. Alternatively, the electrolyte slurry is casted on a substrate separately. As the coating of the electrolyte onto the finalized electrode foils was not investigated in the SOLIFLY project, additional development is needed to integrate this approach.

The follow-up heat treatment and calendaring can be realized after modifications to existing production lines. After evaporation of the solvents in the drying step, the electrolyte exhibits a dry surface, and a roll-to-roll process was demonstrated in the SOLIFLY project on a pilot-line scale. After calendaring, some degree of adhesion of the electrolyte is observed, while a scaled-up roll-to-roll process still should be feasible.

Figure 5: Potential process chain for the electrolyte manufacturing following a conventional approach with medium degree adjustments.

2.4 Cell Assembly

The cell assembly again is closely related to the conventional pouch cell production process, however low-mid level adjustments are needed caused by the handling of the electrolyte.

Preferably, the separation of the electrodes laminated with the semi-solid electrolyte is punched into the preferred dimensions and forms using established punching tools. If the electrolyte is not casted on the electrode foils, automated separation of the electrolyte from the substrate foil needs to be developed based on established technologies.

The stacking of the electrode/gel electrolyte prepregs can be done employing automatic stacking. The surface of the gel electrolyte differs from that of the conventional materials, the impact on the stacking process, however, should be minor. For the RMS-concept battery the addition of a separator is not needed, but for the CCF-concept cells, the addition of cellulose-based separator is needed by now. The optimization of the carbon fibre alignment in a scaled-up process might make the separator unnecessary since the gel electrolyte acts as separator itself. However, the in- or exclusion of the separator resemble only minor adjustments for the stacking process.

The hot pressing of the cell stack is partly being employed for conventional pouch cells already and pressing without increased temperature is done to ensure a good distribution of the conventional, liquid electrolyte. Therefore, the need of hot pressing resembles only a minor or no adjustment on the process level but eventually necessitates the introduction of a hot press unit to the facility, while single cell stacks can be pressed by hot calendaring.

A more severe, possible adjustment can be the introduction of warm isostatic pressing (WIP) to ensure a better interfacial contact in the cell stack. In contrast to calendaring, isostatic pressing is employing pressure uniformly from all sides (isostatic) by the compression of a pressure medium (see Figure 6). For temperatures of about <math><150\text{ }^\circ\text{C}</math>, oil or water are typically employed and pressures of 500-600 MPa are reached [6].

Figure 6: Schematic illustrations of the pressure (straight arrows) effecting the cell stack during calendaring (left) and isostatic pressing (right). The pouch bag containing the cell stack was omitted for clarity.

In the case of the gel electrolyte this process might be a way to prevent squeezing out the ionic liquid from the gel electrolyte. When calendaring a cell stack, the thicker parts of the stack face higher pressure than the thinner ones resulting in areas with higher or lower compression and stress distribution inside the materials [7]. The introduction of WIP would necessitate further development project, but since isostatic pressing is thought to be a suitable process in the large-scale production of all solid-state batteries, process knowledge is present in the battery production industry [6]. Since WIP is employing a liquid pressure medium, the cell stacks needed to be packed and vacuum sealed in a pouch before the compression step. The calendaring of the electrodes in the manufacturing steps before would still be necessary to reduce the porosity of the active materials.

Following the more conventional process, the incorporation of the cell stack into the ply material does not necessitate a sealing of the stack into a pouch, however, for transportation and a safe handling of the cells, a sealing or packaging is essential. This can be achieved by inserting the cell stack into a pouch bag and established sealing methods such as hot sealing or ultrasonic welding.

Before the sealing, the tab welding can be done following the established process, with adjustments for the introduction to the ply. The welding of the carbon fibres to the tab needs to be further explored.

Figure 7: Potential process chain for the cell assembly following a conventional approach with medium degree adjustments.

2.5 Structural Integration and Cell Finishing

The structural integration and cell finishing are the processes with the highest degree of uncertainty as no integrated process is currently industrially established. Two possible processes are being discussed here that are applicable to both cell concepts:

The conventional approach incorporates the cell finishing after assembly of the stack including the sealing into a pouch. This battery cell is then handled as a conventional cell and formation and potentially degassing of the formatting gasses is performed employing existing battery production processes. The finalized cell can then be transported to the composite manufacturer. In this approach, testing of the cells can be done before transportation to the composite manufacturer and non-functional cells can be sorted out.

Care should be taken during the transportation, since the integration of the batteries into plies implies that in the case of a failure of the electrochemical part of the structural battery necessitates the exchange of the whole ply.

Figure 8: Potential process chain for the cell finishing and structural integration of the battery cells into the plies. In this approach, the cell is finished first and then integrated into the composite.

The other possible procedure resembles a more integrated approach. The assembled cells are transported to the composite manufacturer and the integrated battery is being transported back to the battery manufacturer for formatting. Potential degassing should be avoided as puncturing of the ply and sealing after degassing will negatively impact the mechanical properties of the structurally integrated battery. Additional development projects might be needed in order to optimize the cell chemistry and minimize the gas evolution.

Additional to the uncertainty of the degassing step, this approach has two further drawbacks: First, the delay of the cell assembly and the formation of the cell might negatively impact the performance of the battery. As such investigations were not in the scope of this project, decomposition reactions cannot be completely ruled-out. Secondly, non-functional battery cells can only be identified in the testing after the integration in the ply, leading to higher costs per unit upon rejection of the cell.

Figure 9: Potential process chain for the cell finishing and structural integration of the battery cells into the plies. In this approach, the cell is finished after integration into the composite.

On the side of the composite manufacturer, the production process is also impacted by the incorporation of the finished cell stack into composite parts. Therefore, additional development is needed to establish industrial processes capable of the production of structural batteries. A potential process is starting with ply prepregs with cut-outs for the battery cells. The cell can be introduced to the intended position and fixed by sticking to the prepreg surface. After sealing of the prepreg, the position of the cell can be followed by X-ray imaging through the process if needed.

After incorporation of the battery cells into the ply prepregs, the composite is cured, in SOLIFLY using autoclave-curing. This step needs additional development as the incorporation of the battery cells may necessitate different handling of the ply prepregs and further optimization of the curing process. In SOLIFLY the curing process was adapted to ensure compatibility with the battery material. However, to broaden the use of structural battery cells, other ply-materials or manufacturing processes should be considered as well.

2.6 Conclusion of the manufacturability assessment

In conclusion, the manufacturability of the developed structural batteries is mostly impacted by the introduction of coated carbon fibers as electrodes and the structural integration of the battery cells into the composite material.

For concept #2, the RMS cells, an industrial-scaled manufacturability seems feasible after mid-level adjustments to established technologies, which need additional development projects for single steps. Due to the addition of electrolyte formulation to the active material slurries, new production lines need to be procured consisting of machinery and equipment for the coating, drying, and calendaring. The implementation of a warm isostatic press would necessitate additional development but could improve the battery cell performance. Additional investments into the current infrastructures are needed for mixing of the slurries and the punching unit.

For concept #1, the CCF cells, additional investments to all adjustments necessary for concept #2 are needed. This eventually includes a unit to spread carbon tows and additional investments into the development of a suitable coating process. Overall, the handling of the carbon fibers in the battery production process is leading to a higher degree of uncertainty for a potential industrial-scale process.

From an economic point-of-view, the high costs for transportation of the cells from the cell manufacturer to the composite manufacturer need to be considered if the battery cells are finalized before structural integration. If the structural integration is done before the cell finishing, the economic impact of the transportation costs is less severe. However, considering an estimated scrap-rate of at least 5 % in a large-scale production line [8], and higher scrap-rates in smaller production lines and during the run-up phase, the costs of the composite material are increased, since testing of the battery can only be done after the structural integration.

From an ecological perspective, second life applications or recycling processes should be developed to separate the battery cell components from the composite material to enable a return of the raw materials to the value chain after the end of life or end of use.

3. Technology Readiness Level

In order to evaluate the current state of the technology of the structural integrated battery developed in this project, an assessment of the technology readiness level (TRL) is a suitable tool to predict the need and content of future development projects.¹ The assessment of the technology readiness level based on the results of WP2 and WP3 and the manufacturability assessment from this report is given in section 3.1 (TRL Assessment). A more detailed assessment of the TRL of the active materials, the structural electrolyte, battery cell and the final structural integrated battery is given in the subsections 3.1.2-3.1.6.

As the project’s goal is to provide a demonstrator of a structural battery/ply composite and testing of such in a controlled lab environment, the achievable TRL is limited to 4 as no relevant environment validation is in the scope of SOLIFLY.

3.1 TRL Assessment

The SotA TRL by the start of the project 2020 was divided into the several technologies involved into this project. This report is following this scheme. The battery cell technologies used in this project regarding the material level and the two cell concept CCF (concept #1) and RMS (concept #2) are discussed on cell level in the subsections 3.1.2-3.1.5. The TRL of the aeronautic structural battery module as TRL on module level is discussed in subsection 3.1.6. For each subsection, a brief conclusion of the TRL assessment as given followed by a more detailed discussion of relevant aspects for the TLR assessment of the material.

Table 1: State-of-the-art TRL at the start of the SOLIFLY project and the final achieved TRL. For the assessment, the demonstrator was divided in different materials level.

	TRL SotA 2020	Achieved TRL in SOLIFLY
NMC as active material for structural batteries*	1 (CCF), 4 (RMS)	3 (CCF), 4 (RMS)
Structural Electrolyte	3	4
Battery cell concept #1 (multifunctional materials – CCF)	2	3
Battery cell concept #2 (multifunctional elements – RMS)	2-3	4
Structural battery integrated into a representative aeronautic part (stiffened panel)	1	4(-)

*In the SOLIFLY project a pure carbon-based anode active material was used instead of the first proposed Si/C composition.

¹ Coherently with the TRL definition of the H2020, WP 2014-15, Annex G

3.1.1 KPIs of proposal

The following electrochemical and mechanical KPIs were targeted in the SOLIFLY proposal.

Table 2: Selected electrochemical and mechanical KPIs targeted in the SOLIFLY proposal.

Battery cell concept	CCF	RMS
Energy density at material level	140 mAh/g @ 3.6 V, i.e. 500 Wh/kg	
Energy density at cell level	100 mAh/g	180 mAh/g
Nom. Discharge rate	1C	
Number of cycles at 90 % capacity retention	> 300	
Mechanical tests	Full compressive, bending, tensile characterization, 3-point bending	

3.1.2 NMC as active material for structural batteries

The approach to switch from, less advanced active materials, such as LFP, to established, high energy alternatives finally used in the SOLIFLY project, lead to a high TRL of the pure active materials. However, the TRL of the incorporation of these materials into structural batteries by the start of the project was considered low with TRLs of TRL 1 for concept #1 (CCF) and TRL 4 for concept #2 (RMS). The development of suitable slurry recipes, which allowed the coating of the current collectors and enabled a working structural RMS-type battery cell, was validated in a lab environment and therefore TRL 4 is achieved for the RMS battery concept. The CCF concept was not tested implemented to the final demonstrator therefore TRL 3 is proposed.

Starting materials:

At start of the SOLIFLY project, an NMC-based cathode and Si/C-based anode was targeted. However, during the battery cell development a purely carbon-based active material for the anode was favoured due to better chemical stability. The use of graphite-based anodes is more matured compared to Si/C compositions despite ongoing progress [9]. Therefore, on material level, a higher TRL could be leveraged for the incorporation of the active material into a structural battery.

As the active materials used in in the SOLIFLY demonstrator are widely established for conventional pouch cells [10], the maturity of the used starting materials is high.

Slurry recipes:

Although, the active materials used in the project are widespread, established active materials for electrode production, the unconventional concepts of the proposed batteries necessitate the adjustment of current recipes for slurry production to allow the production of the electrodes used in this project. The adjustments achieved throughout this project, ensure the stability of the active material coating and sufficient electrical as well as ionic conductivity.

3.1.3 Structural Electrolyte

The structural electrolyte was considered with TRL 3 by the start of the SOLIFLY project. The developments achieved in the project allowed the use of a safe and pilot-line-scaled manufactured gel electrolyte in both discussed battery cell concepts. While there is room for improvement, the performance of the electrolyte validated in a lab environment meet the requirements in view of safety, electrochemistry, and mechanical properties for its use in a structural battery. It was successfully integrated into functional battery cells. Therefore, TRL 4 was achieved.

Safety:

As the scope of the SOLIFLY project is to deliver a safe battery cell chemistry, considerations regarding to the flammability of the cell components and the evolution of harmful gases after mistreatment of the cells need to be validated. In contrast to the widely used liquid electrolytes consisting of LiPF_6 or other lithium salts solved in highly flammable organic solvents, the ionic liquid and the polymers used in the gel-electrolyte are not flammable. Additionally, it was shown, that the exposure of the electrolyte to humidity in air does not lead to the evolution of highly toxic hydrofluoric acid. Therefore, the overall high safety standard of the electrolyte was successfully validated in a lab environment. If the stability of the electrolyte would allow the omitting of a dry room a clear benefit in sights of CAPEX and OPEX could be achieved. Within SOLIFLY, processing of the electrolyte entirely at ambient conditions could not be tested, however, the available data shows that the developed formulation is very promising in this regard.

Manufacturability:

The manufacturing of gel electrolyte sheets was demonstrated in a pilot-scale production line and the electrolyte was successfully integrated into working battery cells of both concepts.

Electrochemistry:

The ionic conductivity of the structural electrolyte is in the range of liquid electrolyte considering the additional ionic resistance caused by the separator [11] [12]. Since the structural electrolyte itself acts as a separator, the use of an additional separator is not needed in concept #2 RMS. However, in the battery concept #1 CCF, a separator is employed to avoid internal short circuit due to fibre misalignment. The gel electrolyte exhibits therefore sufficient conductivity properties for its use in a battery cell.

The employed ions in the gel electrolyte, however, lead to limitations of its use in the current state. The thermal stability of the structural electrolyte was found to be lower than the CFRP curing temperature proposed by the structural material manufacturer. However, the curing procedure could be adapted, lowering the curing temperature to become compatible with the SB electrolyte without degrading mechanical properties of the CFRP. Also, a C-rate lower than anticipated was reached, but moderate C-rates of up to $C/2$ are still feasible. Despite the successful incorporation of the battery cell into the ply material for the demonstrator, the thermal stability might need improvement, for a broader application without development work for further curing adjustments of the ply materials.

3.1.4 Battery cell concept #1 (multifunctional materials – CCF)

Up to the start of the project, no battery cell was reported consisting of carbon fibre-based anode and cathode in literature. One goal of the SOLIFLY project was a working battery cell following this CCF concept in combination with the semi-solid electrolyte. In terms of the technology readiness level, an increase of TRL1 to TRL4 was formulated to be achieved by the end of the project.

A working battery cell following concept #1 was produced within the SOLIFLY project, however it was not mature enough to be validated in the final demonstrator. Thus, the experimental proof-of-concept of the technology is given with lower than anticipated performance indicators, i.e. a TRL of 3 is reasonable for the battery cell concept #1. Additional development is needed to improve the electrochemical and mechanical performance of the CCF-based battery cell to achieve TRL4. However, the know-how generated in the SOLIFLY project regarding the manufacturing process and handling of the coated carbon fibres and their incorporation into a battery cell should accelerate future development.

Manufacturability:

A lab-scale production process was developed, however further development is needed to ensure the stable and reproducible performance of the battery cell. In some test occasions, short-circuits were

observed, most likely due to misalignment of the carbon fibres, leading to low electrochemical and mechanical performances.

Electrochemistry:

The general functionality of the CCF battery was shown in lab scale by charging and discharging of the assembled cell before the incorporation of the cell into the composite material as reported in D2.1. However, the gravimetric energy density reported (8 Wh/kg) was significantly lower than first proposed (100 Wh/kg) and the targeted charge rate of 1C was not achieved caused by limitations of the semi-solid electrolyte. This problem is thought to partly originate with the manufacturing process of the electrodes and not with the battery cell concept itself.

Mechanical Properties:

The mechanical performance on cell-level was assessed by testing dummy cells. The material proved to be capable of handling high strength stress level upon failure by delamination. However, the existence of initial defects caused by the handling of the carbon fibers limits the mechanical properties of the battery cells. As discussed before, this shortcoming is likely linked to the manufacturing process and not to the battery cell concept itself.

3.1.5 Battery cell concept #2 (multifunctional materials – RMS)

While less significantly, the performance of the RMS battery cell concluded in the lab environment still is below the proposed KPIs. However, the mechanical and electrochemical performances were stable and still feasible for the scope of this project, additionally the scalability of the production process was demonstrated, paving the way for the next TRL-steps. The battery cell concept #2 was validated in a lab and therefore meets the requirements for TRL 4.

Manufacturability:

Pilot-line scalability was demonstrated. The manufactured cells meet the proposed dimensions of a single stack cell.

Electrochemistry:

A specific energy of 50 Wh/kg was achieved, which is approx. 50-72 % below the proposed 100-180 Wh/kg and specific charge values between 40-100 mAh/g_{NMC811} were achieved, which are lower than the proposed 140 mAh/g. However, it was proven that the active material operated with only ionic liquid electrolyte could achieve the expected high energy density. However, in SOLIFLY project it was decided for concept #2 RMS to focus and available efforts on the reproducible and scalable manufacturing of battery cells rather than optimizing further the electrochemistry.

It is worth noting that the proposed KPIs were formulated considering a different cell chemistry.

Overall, the functionality and reproducibility of the RMS battery cell was demonstrated in multiple samples over multiple cycles and different C-rates with a stable performance despite the limitations regarding higher C-rates due to the electrolyte as discussed before. Further optimization of the electrochemical active components as well as weight optimization will be greatly beneficial for the electrochemical performance KPIs of the structural battery.

Mechanical performance:

The mechanical properties of the RMS concept battery cells were proved to be sufficient for its incorporation into the plies. The final failure in a tensile loading test occurs in the area of interest. The failure is associated with delamination of the batteries' layers.

3.1.6 Aeronautic structural battery module (stiffened panel)

The TRL of the structural battery module is directly impacted by the maturity of its components above. Due to its better manufacturing scalability, only RMS-type battery cells were implemented into the structural battery module demonstrator. The demonstrator was electrochemically and mechanically tested in a lab environment and both functionalities were validated. Therefore, TRL4(-) was reached for the RMS structural battery module, indicating that the functionality is given, but further improvements are needed to finally achieve TRL4 in full. The detailed test results for the RMS structural battery module are included in deliverable D3.2 (confidential). [13]

Manufacturability:

An adapted curing cycle was developed (reducing the standard curing temperature of 180°C to 130°C but increasing the curing duration) which did not lead to a decrease in mechanical or electrochemical performance of the CF structure and the SB cells. This additional development was necessary since the normally applied curing conditions damaged the battery cells in earlier manufacturing attempts. Therefore, the curing conditions were one of the biggest challenges for the manufacturability of the structural battery module. Electrical isolation with Kapton foil in the demonstrator led to delamination of the ply.

The adapted curing cycle could be applied to any industrial epoxy CF material that has maximum curing temperature of 180°C. This enables the integration of structural battery cells in any epoxy thermoset composite material.

Electrochemistry:

The RMS structural battery module showed electrochemical functionality and was charged and discharged over multiple cycles. Therefore, a proof-of-concept regarding the electrochemistry is given. However, some of the integrated cells were not functional in the demonstrator and self-discharge of the cells was observed after integration into the ply material, which might be avoidable by adapting the electrical insulation of the cells inside the ply.

Mechanical performance:

The delamination introduced by the electrical insulation did decrease the buckling mode of the composite material. This lower-than-expected buckling mode can be linked to the delamination within the composite material and was probably caused by the electrical integration. Despite that, the structural battery demonstrator showed load bearing capabilities with given electrochemical functionality during the mechanical tests.

Results in detail:

- A new updated curing cycle was defined in order to preserve the battery cells and obtain functional elements.
- A reference carbon/epoxy stiffened panel has been designed by simulation containing 3 T-stringers. The first buckling mode and load have been accurately predicted with finite element simulation. At buckling load, the panel did not break, meaning the mechanical properties of such a structure are very high.
- A panel with 20 structural battery cells (SOLIFLY demonstrator) was designed and manufactured by a subcontractor. RMS cells developed by AIT were introduced into the skin of the panel. Applied measures to electrically insulate the cells (insulation spray and Kapton around the cells' tabs) proved insufficient from electrical and mechanical point of view (the latter leading to the occurrence of initial delamination cracks).

- The global stiffness of the SOLIFLY demonstrator panel with cells is similar to that of the reference panel, what validates the proposed panel design. Nevertheless, due to the presence of initial delamination cracks, the first bucking load was only 50% of that of the reference panel. However, the structural battery panel is still able to carry out 18 tons without any failure, which matches our initial goal in the SOLIFLY project.
- The electrical performance of the panel was qualitatively evaluated before, during and after the mechanical loading:
 - 80% (16) of the integrated SB cells can be rated as functional. Only 4 out of 20 seem not to be chargeable.
 - Insufficient electrical insulation results in high scattering on the charge/discharge behavior of the functional cells and prevents evaluating quantitatively their performance.
 - Nevertheless, normalisation of the charge indicator showed that the AIT cells seem rather insensitive to the applied loading.

The obtained results are very promising, but many works remain. The most important point should consist in evaluating technologies to improve electrical isolation while maintaining good adhesion between the cell and the composite material, in order to obtain high residual properties for the structure.

3.2 TRL step-up plan

The technology developed in the SOLIFLY project was evaluated in the section above and TRL4(-) was reached for the RMS structural battery module demonstrator. Therefore, the general functionality of the demonstrator was confirmed in a lab environment and its KPIs were determined from a stable and repeatable performance. However, a number of challenges were identified at the current stage, which need to be addressed in further development of the technology. This section lists the challenges identified at the current stage and provides a list of requirements for the TRL-step-up.

Challenges identified at the current stage:

At the current stage, a number of challenges was identified, which need to be addressed to achieve TRL 4 in full and step-up to next TRL.

- SB electrochemical and structural performance:
 - On the level of the active materials, the originally proposed Si/C-based anode will improve electrochemical performance. To do so, the stability issues of the silicon-containing material need to be addressed.
 - The handling of the carbon fibres for cell concept #1 CCF is causing issues on cell level at its current stage. The optimized processing of the carbon fibres might be easily achievable after scaling up the production process and enable a higher degree of automation. This will minimize the probability of initial defects, which can negatively impact the electrochemical and mechanical properties of the battery cells in their current stage. The electrochemical performance can be further enhanced by optimizing the coating process of the carbon fibres to ensure a good ratio of homogenous active material and the carbon fibres.
 - The electrolyte in its current state is limited in its C-rate capability and thermal stability but approaches to counter both issues were already identified. The mechanical properties of the gel electrolyte might be enhanced by optimization of the content of nano particles.
 - The currently lower than proposed electrochemical performances of the battery cells are mainly caused by the challenges identified on material and electrolyte level. Reducing the weight-percentage of electrochemical non-active materials can further increase the specific energy on cell level.
- Structural performance (other than the electrolyte):

- RMS: for the RMS approach the structural performance can be readily improved by targeting the adhesion between the electrode loading and the current collectors. This interface has been identified as the main bottleneck for load transfer and thus structural performance. Furthermore, integration of 1D conductive additives like carbon fibers or carbon nanotubes might further improve the performance.
- CCF: the fibre volume fraction needs to be improved. The alignment of the CCF electrodes needs to be further improved to achieve homogenous mechanical properties within the composite material.
- Final integration and demonstration
 - The SOLIFLY demonstrator did not include CCF type battery cells. A scalable manufacturing procedure for the CCF battery cells needs to be established leading to a stable performance of the cells. After the coated carbon fibre cells proved to show reliable functionality, a demonstrator employing CCF-cells should get tested.
 - Improvements in the battery cell design and chemistry are needed to boost the performance of the structural battery.
 - In the final SOLIFLY demonstrator, RMS cells have been integrated achieving 80% of them being functional after curing. However, electrical insulation issues need to be improved to implement battery cells into the ply material with low failure rate.
 - The delamination within the demonstrator was probably caused by the electrical integration and negatively impacted the mechanical performance and therefore needs to be improved. However,

Various areas relevant to aerospace structural battery have not been addressed in SOLIFLY but need further research:

- SB safety:
 - Fire safety: Even if SOLIFLY SB electrochemistry is conceived for and its integration concept suggests high battery safety (using non-flammable ionic liquid, high surface-to-thickness ratio of the cells, integrated in solid CFRP laminates with similar or higher thermal conductivity as the SB cells), the abuse behavior of SOLIFLY SB technology needs to be evaluated in detail, especially under realistic failure cases. Such tests require SB cells with higher capacity (at least 1 Ah) than available in SOLIFLY.
 - Structural safety: Delamination between SB cell layers and between the CFRP structure and the SB cell (e.g. in case of low-energy (drop-tool) impact) needs to be understood better.
- SB life vs structural life: The apparent gap between rather short SB cycling life and much longer structural life will need to be reduced – fully closing it seems hardly feasible even if for today's Li-ion battery electrochemistries). This needs to be done at various levels: from electrochemistry level to part/system level where the system design will need to account for multifunctional life and monitoring the multifunctional state of health with integrated sensing will become key.
- SB integration concepts, structural materials, maintenance/repair/recyclability
 - Exploring SB integration into sandwich CFRP structures and utilizing currently unused voids to enlarge the design space for electrical energy integration.
 - Improve compatibility of airworthy structural materials and SB electrochemistry. Low curing temperature or using alternative approaches (e.g. UV cure) would be favorable for SB electrochemistry. Thermoplastic materials would be beneficial for dismantling and recycling of SB parts, however the very high melting temperature of common thermoplastics exceeds the thermal stability of battery active materials.

- The electrical integration (insulation, wiring and module layout) needs to be further developed.

The sister and follow-up project MATISSE (GA 101056674, <https://www.matisse-project.eu/>; <https://doi.org/10.3030/101056674>) will develop further SB technology by tackling several of the challenges indicated above. It aims at qualifying the technology still at TRL 4 proposedly in 2025 in a full-scale demonstration in the lab of a smart structural battery module (with integrated sensing and monitoring) in a non-safety-critical, curved, external aircraft part (a removeable wing-tip for the Pipistrel Velis electro).

TRL 5

The step-up from TRL 4 to TRL 5 is achieved, when the technology is validated in a relevant environment. A suitable approach could be the design of a more advanced prototype, with (almost) final positioning of the battery cells as a modular building piece for incorporation into an aircraft. The validation of the performance should be done in smaller steps. First, a large modular structural battery module, incorporated into non-critical parts of an aircraft should be subject to an electrochemical testing routine while simulating realistic loads in a representative flight mission. In parallel, the mechanical properties are accessible through extensive simulations. Finally, both aspects of the technology might be tested under a relevant environment in a (climatic) wind tunnel or large mechanical and environmental test facility with simultaneously applying power loads onto the batteries, simulating a flight mission, e.g. typical for a light general aviation aircraft. The interplay between structures with and without internal batteries should also be addressed.

The identification of the target applications and market is key. The requirements for the technology for a real-life application should be identified with expertise from aircraft manufacturer. While the technology is maturing, different non-propulsive applications with lower electrochemical performance requirements can be realized with the structured battery integrated in non-safety critical parts before structural batteries contribute to the propulsion of smaller aircrafts starting from TRL 5. TRL 5 is proposed to be reached through research and innovation actions between 2028-2032 (see Figure 10).

TRL 6

For the step-up from TRL 5 to TRL 6, a demonstration of the technology in a realistic environment is needed. This necessitates the production of a full-scale prototype. In case of the structural battery, this at first might be a modular structural battery part, which can be integrated into a conventional aircraft, to early identify technical issues in a realistic environment before implementation of the aimed amount of structural battery into a hybrid-electric aircraft. Again, if suitable, adapted simulations of the structural battery included into an aircraft should be done, before the incorporation, ground tests and first flight tests. During this stage, the manufacturability of the structural battery should be demonstrated on a larger scale. Development of a small-scale production line for the battery cells as well as a scalable process for the incorporation of the cells into the plies should be achieved. This step-up will require solid funding as well as technical expertise from aerospace corporations.

TRL 7

At TRL 7 a production process of the battery containing composites should be well established to manufacture multiple full-scale prototypes and perform test missions under miscellaneous conditions. This way, the technology can be proofed to be reliable and fulfils operational requirements. The operational requirements need to be identified together with potential customer (e.g., aircraft manufacturer) and meet their expectations. Additionally, regulations and standards should be addressed. At this stage, product development can be started, and dissemination of the reliability and innovativeness should be focussed to

demonstrate the maturity of the technology. The benefits of the incorporation of structural batteries into future zero-emission CS-23 and CS-25 aircraft (as developed by Clean Aviation and to enter in service from 2035 on) should be highlighted. TRL 7 for the SOLIFLY technology is expected to be achievable between 2032-2040.

TRL 8 & TRL 9

TRL 8 requires a complete and qualified system. The modular battery composites should be in their final design and should be ready to be tested by aircraft manufacturer in their commercial setting (expected conditions and periods). Full-scale production of the structural batteries plies needs to be employed. At this stage, the commercialization of the technology is in focus. Stable and reproducible performance are key for a wide-spread use of the batteries and the development of broad market sectors.

The full commercial deployment of the structural battery plies is achieved when a significant market share is reached. For this achievement, customer acquisition and scaling of the production to the needs of the market is needed. The aircraft manufacturer employing the structural batteries in their products should be satisfied with the performance and the technology should be able to compete to conventional energy sources (e.g., fuel). The next step is the development of further markets, such as the implementation in CS-23 and CS-25 aircraft.

Figure 10: Proposed TRL step-up following the SOLIFLY project.

4. Exploitation Plan

The SOLIFLY project generated multiple exploitable results. A survey was conducted to sum up these results and further classify them for the exploitation plan. Most of the exploitable results were classified as generated knowledge or the development of skills. Additionally, prototypes, processes and protocols were developed or improved. Most results were generated in the battery cell development. A summary of most results was already presented in the final workshop of WP4 (November 20-21, 2023 in Naples). The MATISSE project will pick up results from the SOLIFLY projects and further improve the structural battery technology. In the next 1-5 years exploitation of the results will dominantly be exploited as part of co-funded research while the exploitation in product and service design is anticipated at earliest in five years. These general exploitation routes are proposed:

1. Structural battery cell design and manufacturing

The know-how generated in the SOLIFLY project will be used to further improve the aspects of both concepts of structural batteries employed. The gained knowledge will boost future research activities at AIT and UNIVIE and will accelerate the maturing of both technologies. This will help increasing the TLR from its current state closer to commercialization. To achieve TRL 6, the manufacturability on a larger scale of the battery cells should be demonstrated. Once there is an identified demand for a semi-solid-state batteries, and the technology is mature enough to compete with established batteries, CCI will internally exploit the insights in the manufacturing process in their product development. After identifying and solving of technical issues of the battery cells in a realistic setting and established production procedures, additional markets can be developed. While the SOLIFLY project is focused on aerospace application, structural batteries will also be important for other industries such as heavy-duty mobility applications (rail, maritime) or the use in portable devices and robotics once the costs for structural batteries can compete with conventional batteries due to more efficient use of space. The development of those sectors will be tackled by minor tweaks of the generated know-how on cell chemistry, design level and manufacturing level to reach a broad market. CCI will transfer manufacturing knowledge to large scale cell manufacturers.

2. Structural battery ply manufacturing

Complementing the exploitation routes described for the battery cell design and manufacturing, design and manufacturing of multifunctional composite structures becomes important. Due to the low TRL of the technologies used in the SOLIFLY projects, those activities will be performed mainly by research and technology organizations such ONERA. After the SOLIFLY technology will reach TRL 6, the know-how will be transferred to the industry.

3. Airworthiness

The third exploitation route is less research orientated, than the battery cell design, manufacturing, and implementation, but necessitates policy making. Since the aviation sector is heavily regulated and strict safety standards are in place, the demands on the structural battery composites need to be surveyed and monitored over the whole maturing period, while a participation in the design of future regulations for (hybrid) electric large aircraft needs to be constructively targeted.

5. Conclusion

The aim of this deliverable was to assess the outcome of WP2 and WP3 insights of manufacturability and technological maturity as well as of its exploitation.

In the first part of this deliverable, the scaled-up, industrially applicable manufacturability of the SOLIFLY structural battery cell concepts was evaluated. For this assessment, a potential production process was defined for the electrodes, the cells and finally the structural battery for both technology concepts investigated in the SOLIFLY project. The transferability of existing processes was rated and necessary adjustments and adaption from other industries identified. While especially for the production of the RMS-type batteries a high degree of transferability is seen as already given, the handling of the gel electrolyte, the stacking process of the electrodes and the implementation of the battery cells into the plies will make further developments necessary in order to scale-up the manufacturing processes to an industrial level.

The technical maturity of the SOLIFLY technologies was assessed in the second part of this deliverable. This evaluation was achieved by rating the maturity of the final demonstrator on different levels, starting with the employed materials.

In general, the targeted TRL4 was achieved by the SOLIFLY project, however, some aspects indicated lower than anticipated performances. A TRL of 3 was determined for the CCF battery at material level, as the technology was not integrated into the demonstrator and could therefore not be tested as structural battery in a controlled lab environment. However, the proof-of-concept of the active materials used for both CCF and RMS batteries was achieved. The demonstrator employing only RMS-type battery cells showed mechanical and electrical functionality in a controlled lab environment. However, measures applied to insulate the cells electrically from the CFRP structure were not fully effective but impacted multifunctional performance of the demonstrator panel, leading to a TRL of 4(-). The TRL assessment was complemented by a TRL-step-up plan which discussed the problems at the current stage of the technology and the improvements necessary in the future. The MATISSE project is further improving the technology and will offer solutions to the problems identified at the current TRL stage.

Finally, an exploitation plan of the SOLIFLY project results was developed. A survey was conducted, showing that most of the exploitable results can be classified as generated know-how and the development of skills. These will be exploited in the following years in the three general exploitation routes *Structural battery cell design and manufacturing*, *Structural battery ply manufacturing* and *Airworthiness*.

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Project partners

Participant No*	Participant short name	Participant organisation name	Country
1. (Coord.)	AIT	AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH	Austria
2.	ONERA	Office national d'études et de recherches aérospatiales	France
3.	CCI	Custom Cells Itzehoe GmbH	Germany
4.	UNIVIE	University of Vienna	Austria
5.	UNINA	Università degli Studi di Napoli Federico II	Italy
6.	CIRA	Centro Italiano Ricerche Aerospaziali	Italy

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